

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING PROCESS IN UNITED ENTERPRISES, COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

Employees are the most valuable asset of an organization, so to enhance their performance it is necessary to pay attention to their learning. Training and development programs help organizations to build a skilled and competent workforce in order to maintain a high level of competency and to survive in a dynamic business environment. This study was conducted with the aim to investigate the effectiveness of training and development on employee performance at United Enterprises, Coimbatore. The research employed descriptive analysis. Primary data was collected through distributing questionnaires to 100 employees, who were selected through the random sampling technique. Findings reveal that overall training and development has a significant impact on employee's performance. It helps the organization in reducing employee turnover, increasing the productivity of employees, and contributing to higher financial returns for the organization. The study suggests that there is a need for improvisation in identifying the area where training needs have actually generated and salary structure should be revised at a regular interval of time.

Key Words: Training, Development, Employee Performance, Organization.

Introduction:

The definition of training effectiveness refers to the measurement of the impact on learners' knowledge, skills, and performance. It also refers to the company's return on investment. Generally, training effectiveness is how well training supports learning and the transfer of training. Organizations must clearly define the training's goals and objectives to accurately measure and evaluate training effectiveness. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) defines the purpose of training as helping improve the learner's competence, capacity, and performance. But businesses may have more specific metrics.

Importance:

Learning and Development (L&D) teams often must prove training programs' return on investment (ROI). Organizational leaders want to know if invested resources like time, money, and energy are worth the expense. Plus, training evaluations help organizations identify if training achieved their intended outcomes. Organizational administration can use them to make decisions about future programs. L&D leaders who have the data ready when asked can prove the program's worth. Not only can having ways to measure the ROI of training and development help them avoid budgetary cuts, but it can also improve their request for an increase in funding.

Reasons to Measure the Effectiveness of Training and Development:

- To determine if the training benefits employees' skills and performance
- To find out what participants achieved
- To discover the path employees need to take to reach their next professional milestone
- To uncover issues in the training process and improve it
- To convert the training impact into additional revenue
- Furthermore, effective training leads to the following:
 - Higher employee performance and satisfaction
 - Boosts in team morale, engagement, and company culture
 - Positive encouragement about what participants did well
 - Beneficial feedback about where employees can improve
 - Improved HR metrics like better retention and recruiting

Why Measure Training Effectiveness?

To Determine if the Training Benefits Employees:

Perhaps the most important reason for evaluating training effectiveness is to see if it benefits your employees' skills and performance. Additionally, it provides them with a clear idea of what they've achieved and the path they need to take to get to the next level. When it comes to learning and development (L&D), feedback and encouragement are crucial. Virtually all employees need positive encouragement for the things they've done well and want to know how to improve. Without measurements in place, your employees are likely to feel that their learning at work is purposeless. Evaluating your training effectiveness helps you communicate to your employees where the company is today and where it aims to go, along with the skills necessary to get there. Consequently, managers and employees can come together and discuss the results, helping employees feel empowered and part of the broader vision.

To See the Effect on Business Performance and Determine the Training's ROI:

The ultimate goal of all training programs is to boost business performance and see a return on your investment. Changes in productivity, sales, and profits can all be tracked and measured, and you would hope to see an increase in all of the above. Studies have shown that organizations who regularly invest in training perform higher than those who don't, but it must be the right type of training, and it must be meticulously tracked and measured. For example, it's difficult to determine whether the training in question was responsible for an increase in sales, or if it was the result of something else, like a marketing campaign or a boost in the economy. This is why it's important to examine things like learning transfer and noticeable behavioral changes that may have taken place since the training program.

To Uncover Issues in the Training Process and Improve It:

When you invest valuable resources like time, money, and energy into your training programs, it's essential to measure whether they're working or not. But your intentions for your training will be unique to your business and your long-term goals. This is why you need to define clear objectives at the start. If you fail to do this, then any results you receive will be meaningless because you don't have a target in sight. Once you know where you're heading and your desired outcome, measuring training effectiveness will help you see if you're on the right track or if you need to make any adjustments. If a particular training program is highly effective, it can be implemented across the board, from executives to managers and new hires. This helps unite the company with shared goals. And if training fails to produce any desirable results, you need to determine why and where this breakdown happens and then make adjustments accordingly. For example, in the ADDIE model of instructional design, evaluation is an integral part of each phase of learning development process. That enables L&D professionals and trainers to continuously improve the training to achieve learning goals.

Types of Training Methods:

Most training methods target more than one learning style, whereas some focus on one particular style. And that's okay because if you offer training using different types of methods, you'll satisfy the styles of different employees. And unless the topic calls for a particular training method, you might even offer a variety of methods for a single topic. You can also give your staff options to learn in different ways depending on the circumstances. For instance, they might wish to learn by listening on one day and by watching on another. Below are seven of the best types of employee training methods:

- Case Studies
- Coaching
- e Learning
- Instructor-Led Training
- Interactive Training
- On-the-Job Training
- Video-Based Training

Check out the details and benefits of each type!

Case Studies:

This type of training is great for developing critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills. The scenarios can be real or imaginary, but in the context of employee training, they all illustrate situations at work. Learners read the case studies and then analyze and solve them individually or in a group. Some solutions might be better than others, depend on assumptions, and be either optimal or the best possible given the circumstances. Although case studies allow your staff to learn at their own pace, they're most useful for less complex topics.

Coaching:

Mentor-ship-another name for coaching-should be an impactful and memorable learning experience. At least, that's the expectation of mentors and mentees. When your experienced staff dedicates time and effort to coaching new employees, those new employees will feel valued and supported. Put some emphasis on the time and effort required by mentors, and remember that it pays off. Although coaching and on-the-job training might seem similar, coaching:

- Focuses on the mentor-mentored relationship
- Is more inspiring
- Is most likely to make the employee comfortable asking questions

You can also deliver coaching sessions online-making them even more accessible.

E Learning:

You might know this one by online training. It's computer-based training that's delivered from a distance, online. The advantages?

- Learners can go through the content and activities at their own pace.
- There's no need to hire an instructor.
- It scales beautifully, so the number of simultaneous learners can increase tremendously.

Oftentimes, this type of training:

- Resembles classroom training
- Uses visuals with a voice over
- Complements lessons with videos and reading materials

As you don't have an instructor monitoring engagement levels, you must use other means to do it. Quizzes and other types of interactive activities are wonderful for that purpose. They also allow you to appraise the progress of each employee and the effectiveness of the training.

Instructor-Led Training:

Whether it's in-person or online, an instructor-led training session is very much based on the dynamics of a classroom.

- Led by an instructor

- With a presentation-just like a lecture
- Although an academic-like classroom experience may not seem thrilling to some learners, the method has some significant pros.
- Learners can ask the instructor questions that the materials don't cover in real-time.
- Instructors can monitor learners' progress and engagement.
- Learners and instructors can build a relationship with each other.
- Complex topics are sometimes easier to teach in a classroom.

On the other hand, whether they're online or physical, classrooms-or instructor-led training sessions-have some cons.

- A high number of learners prevents the instructor from interacting one-on-one with all of them.
- Learners can't learn at their own pace since there are multiple learners in the (in-person or virtual) room.

Interactive Training:

Anything interactive has the potential to grab our attention. And training is no different! That's why interactive training is highly engaging and effective. Learners absorb more information, retain it faster, and recall it for longer periods of time. The success of interactive training comes from being practical rather than theoretical. So, employees learn by applying knowledge in a realistic setting. Here are three examples of interactive training:

- **Game Based Training:** Using rewards like points increases motivation levels, and this type of training can make learning fun.
- **Role Playing:** A facilitator manages the process of acting out different work scenarios with the learners. It's especially effective for client or customer interaction training as it explores difficult situations in a controlled environment.
- **Simulations:** These can be appropriate for learning specialized, complex skills, like for medicine or aviation training. Simulations set up real work scenarios for the learners, so augmented or virtual reality can be great simulation tools.

On-the-Job Training:

Also known as hands-on training, on-the-job training is all about the practical skills that a job requires. Therefore, the employee learns by going through the experience of executing real activities at work. On-the-job training reduces the time before the employee starts performing their job function. It can take different forms, such as:

- **Internships:** Interns obtain guidance, support, and training from the company that hired them. And the more prior knowledge they have of what the job entails, the better for their future success.
- **Rotations:** Job rotations boost employee motivation, satisfaction, cooperation, and commitment to the company. By exposing the employee to different business areas of your company, they develop skills they might not otherwise have and a deeper understanding of and commitment to the company as a whole. This increases retention levels and your employees' chances of moving up in their own department or in another.
- **Shadowing:** New hires observe existing employees while they work, ask questions, and sometimes help with tasks. By doing that, new hires understand how they'll have to do their work before they actually have to do it.

Employee engagement-or interest and involvement-is vital for the success of on-the-job training. Engagement is typically heightened with on-the-job training since it's individual and the learning activities intimately relate to the employee's job. On-the-job training produces results quickly and is also appropriate for teaching and developing leadership skills.

Video-Based Training:

Speed and efficiency-these are the keywords that propelled video as an employee training vehicle. Additionally, it became popular because it can be way more interesting than traditional training methods. It's highly engaging and can be entertaining as well! Animations raise information recall to impressive levels. Live-action videos are great for demonstrations. Webinars and screen recordings of step-by-step procedures can take a simple list and turn it into an entertaining, story-based how-to. Video-based training is easily accessible and repeatable-the employee can watch the video as many times as they need. Also, it doesn't require an instructor. Now that you know each one of the types of training methods for employees, are you ready to choose? Here are some tips on making the right choice for your organization.

Objective of the Study:

Primary Objectives:

- To study the Effectiveness of Training process in United Enterprises, Coimbatore

Secondary Objective:

- To find out the training process programme provided by united enterprises
- To evaluate job related knowledge to the employees
- To evaluate equipment handling practices and employees for advancement.
- To find out the overall productivity and performance levels of an employees
- To find out the motivation level of the employees towards training process programme.

Need for the Study:

Technology is responsible for increased need of training inputs to employees, it is important to understand that there are other factors too that contribute to the latter. Training is also necessary for the individual development and progress of the employee, which motivates him to work for a certain organization apart from just money. We also require training update employees of the marked trends, the change in the employment policies and other things.

Purpose of the Study:

The Purpose of the Effectiveness of Training Process is to:

- Organize and facilitate learning and development
- Expedite acquisition of the knowledge, skills, and abilities require for effective job performance
- Provide employees with career growth opportunities consistent with corporate goals, objectives, and strategies.

- Building more efficient, effective and highly motivated team, which enhances the company's competitive position and improves employee morale.
- It also needs in order to improve the employee's performance in the Organization

Scope of the Study:

The development of any organization depends on the employees, for organizational productivity training programme assume great significance.

- The study is conducted to know the level of knowledge and skill given to the employees in the organization
- This will help the management to know the satisfaction levels of employees and they can take measure to increase productivity
- This study may help the management students to prepare their own report
- Tends to be narrowly focused and oriented towards short - term performance concerns.

Sources of Data Collection:

The sources of information for the study are employees (Workmen and Executives) I have also used Primary data and Secondary data

Primary Data:

Primary data is term used in number of disciplines to describe source material that is closest to the personal information, period or idea being studied. It includes primary data which collected for the first time for study in United Enterprises. The primary data was collected from the respondents by administering a structured questionnaire and also through observation with management.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data refers to the data which has already been collected by someone else and which has already published. A part from primary data collected, though a text book, the record of journals from library, academic report and internet used for the study.

Sample Size:

The sample size of the study is 100 employees in United Enterprises at Coimbatore

Sampling Technique:

The sampling technique is used in this study is Sample Random Sampling. It is the sample of given size in which all such subsets of the frame are given an equal probability to be chosen.

Area of the Study:

The study was conducted among the employees of United Enterprises at Coimbatore.

Period of the Study:

The period of the study is from 18/03/2024 to 15/06/2024. During these periods the researcher collected the necessary primary data and other relevant information needed to be carrying out the study

Researching Instruments Used to Collect Data:

A Structured questionnaire is used and the type of questions format is used based on the research of Likert scale. Likert Scale is the technique used for asking the questions. The Respondent is asked to respond to each of the statements in terms of several degrees as given below.

- SD - Strongly Disagree = 1
- D - Disagree = 2
- N - Neutral = 3
- A - Agree = 4
- SA - Strongly Agree = 5

Analytical Tools for the Study:

The tools used are

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Percentage Analysis Method:

Percentage refers to a special kind of ratio. Percentage is used in making comparison between two or more series of data Percentage can also use to compare the relative terms, the distribution of two or more series of data. The easy simplicity of calculating, the general understanding of its purpose and the universal applicability of the percent static have made it widely and standardizes tool in researcher.

Percentage Analysis Formula:

Percentage of respondents = (No of respondents/Total No of respondents)*100

Chi-Square Test Method:

The Chi-square test is one of the simplest and most widely uses non parametric tests in statistical work. The symbol χ^2 is the Greek letter "Chi." Karl Pearson

Correlation:

Correlation is simply defined as a relationship between the two variables. The purpose of using the correlation in research is to figure out which variables are connected

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Respondents by Their Level of Improvement In Training:

Respondents by Their External Training Sources Performed:

Respondents by Their Employee Relation Rate:

Respondents by Their External Training Sources Performed:

Respondents by Their Resume Screening and Short Listing Method:

Respondents by Their Present Method of Selection Technique:

Respondents by Their Higher Employee Performance:

Suggestions:

- It shows few of the employees are uncertain about the training and development which results in higher employee performance in the organization, which made to suggest management to rework on training content or its training methodologies to focus more increasing efficiency.
- It shows few employees are uncertain about the effectiveness of training program in the organization, this again re-ensure to open new doors to technological inventions within the organization to increase efficiency.
- It shows that the training should be mandatory for all level of the employee.
- The company should give the appropriate recognition for the contributions and accomplishments made by employees.
- A flexible reward system should be adopted by organization to improve employee motivation.
- Also, its suggested to conduct more practical session to its employees for better understanding

Conclusion:

Training has become increasingly vital to the success of modern organization. During the period of my study in united enterprises, Coimbatore. I got an opportunity to understand the importance's of effectiveness of employee training process. Apart from employees are motivated they should also know their strength and weakness. So effectiveness of training process try to improve skills and to the existing level of knowledge .so that the present job or to get prepared for a higher position with increased responsibilities. From the study conducted, most of the employees are satisfied with training process activities.

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